

**THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE USE OF HEALTH-SHAPING
TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TRAINING PROCESS OF YOUNG SAMBO
WRESTLERS**

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Abstract: *Each sport and training process has its own specific features. Similar factors determine the possibility of borrowing training methods and sharing experiences in related sports. However, there may be similar methodological approaches, organization of training management, use of the experience of the recovery service, etc. Creative borrowing of experience is a complex area of professional activity.*

Keywords: *efficiency, technology, sambo wrestler, training, individual, preparation, sport, physical culture.*

Аннотация: *Каждый вид спорта и тренировочный процесс имеет свои специфические особенности. Схожие факторы определяют возможность заимствования методов тренировок и обмена опытом в смежных видах спорта. Однако могут быть схожие методологические подходы, организация управления тренировками, использование опыта службы восстановления и т.д. Творческое заимствование опыта - сложная сфера профессиональной деятельности.*

Ключевые слова: *эффективность, технология, самбист, тренировка, индивидуальная, подготовленность, спорт, физическая культура.*

Annotatsiya: *har bir sport va mashg'ulot jaraëni o'ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega. Shunga o'xshash omillar mashg'ulot usullarini qarzga olish va tegishli sport turlari bo'yicha tajriba almashish imkoniyatini belgilaydi. Biroq, shunga o'xshash uslubiy ëndashuvlar, o'qitishni boshqarishni tashkil etish, tiklash xizmati tajribasidan foydalanish va boshqalar bo'lishi mumkin. Tajribani ijodiy jalb qilish-bu kasbiy faoliyatning murakkab sohasi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *samaradorlik, texnologiya, sambo kurashchisi, mashg'ulot, individual, fitnes, sport, jismoniy madaniyat.*

The main criteria for the effectiveness of optimizing the educational environment of schoolchildren are:

- 1) positive changes in the dynamics of students' health at the somatic, individual-mental, socio-personal, and spiritual-moral levels (criterion of effectiveness),
- 2) appropriate changes in the state of the educational environment from the point of view of preserving and strengthening the health of students (performance criterion),
- 3) to identify the prevailing styles of interaction between participants in the educational process (this task covers a wide range of issues of mental hygiene, including interactions between administration - teacher, teacher - teacher, administration - student, teacher - student, student-parents, etc.).

It is rational to implement an integrated approach to the organization of school health protection based on the program-target method.

Let's consider the stages of program design and the first steps to implement it in the form of an algorithm.:

- 1) Raising the issue of the state of health of modern schoolchildren at the pedagogical council of the school with the involvement of a modern regulatory framework for the protection of children's health, statistical data on the country, region and specific educational institution. Making a decision on the development of the School Children's Health program (provisional name).

- 2) Creation of an initiative group to develop a draft program. In addition to the school administration, it is recommended that teachers of physical education, biology, housing and communal services, a school psychologist, a social teacher and other members of the teaching staff be included in the initiative group on a voluntary basis. If the administration chooses a health problem as a priority for the development of the school, it is recommended to include in the staffing the position of head of health protection, who has sufficient authority to organize and coordinate health-saving activities in the educational institution. It is extremely important for effective work to establish contacts with specialists who deal with this problem professionally, to choose the supervising scientific and practical organization or the scientific director of the program.

- 3) Collecting information. The initiative group, together with the scientific director of the program, collects information on how such work is organized, shares experiences with other educational institutions, selects the necessary literary sources, studies the regulatory framework, selects or independently develops a concept and theoretical model for creating a health-saving educational environment in an educational institution.

- 4) Development of the draft program. Based on the information received, a draft program is being developed. There are various options for developing the program. The strategic program implies the development of the main goals and objectives so that the analysis of the current (current) state of the educational environment is included in

the first stage of the program implementation. This is exactly the design option being considered in this case.

5) The draft program is discussed and adjusted in methodological associations of teachers, on the pedagogical council of the school, in the student council, in the school-wide parent committee. A democratic procedure for its adoption is carried out, areas of responsibility, forms of control, criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of program implementation and reporting are determined. The school administration develops local regulations that reflect changes in the staffing table and the functional responsibilities of specialists in connection with the adoption of the program.

6) Creation of coordinating and executive structures. If there are appropriate specialists in an educational institution, a health service is created, which in this case is entrusted with the task of coordinating actions to implement the program (a health teacher (head teacher), a school psychologist, a social educator, a doctor, a nurse and other specialists), or a coordinating council is formed. In order to attract students to actively participate in the implementation of the program, it is recommended to form student assets (middle and high grades) on a voluntary basis. It is also possible to form a parent's rehabilitation center.

Practical experience suggests that schools tend to underestimate the potential of students and parents in creating a health-friendly educational environment, thereby significantly reducing its effectiveness.

It is not recommended to tackle all tasks at the same time. It seems more rational at the first stage after the initial diagnosis to optimize the organization of the educational process and sanitary and hygienic conditions, then to "adjust" the motor mode of students, etc.

When developing the School Children's Health program, based on the considered theoretical optimization model, the choice of a pedagogical strategy for its implementation is recommended as the dominant one. In this case, the solution of the program's tasks coincides in time and timing with the training of the teaching staff.

Improving the competence of teachers and parents in the field of school health protection and encouraging the administration to participate in health-saving activities. Each of us is more or less dependent on the opinions of others, especially from the opinion of our superiors. The positive attitude of the administration, which should actually turn into active participation in seminars, is significant, as it creates an external motivation for introducing a health-saving component into the professional activity of a teacher. The teacher working at the school today has not studied the theory of personality-oriented education, he has no time to engage in self-education because of the constant overload. If, according to the principle of imitation, teachers begin to master the technologies of personality-oriented education, health-saving technologies,

this can have pronounced negative consequences when the child's personality development does not occur, and the goals of traditional education will not be achieved. In addition, we recall the opinion of Yakimov A.M.: "Personality-oriented education, which is being fully implemented today, may turn out to be maladaptive, since the associated social institutions continue to operate in the knowledge paradigm."

The way out to improve the competence of teachers may be to use the above-mentioned learning system, but with pedagogical content. Once again, we emphasize that revolutionary changes in such matters are impossible, because the primary thing here is a change in professional thinking.

The question arises - what actions can teachers take if the school does not have a specialist capable of providing training in the field of health? First, you can contact the administration yourself with this issue, convince them of the need to find such a specialist. Secondly, you can engage in self-education and self-improvement, starting with a repeated, biased study of the well-known courses "School hygiene", "Age physiology and anatomy", "Age psychology", etc. In addition, in the methodological association, with a group of like-minded colleagues, it is possible to organize mutual learning according to the program discussed above, when each in turn prepares a separate topic and acts as a teacher. Practice shows that the introduction of the above-mentioned activities into the school day in middle and high schools should be preceded by appropriate "propaganda" work with teachers, who may initially be strongly negative. It is necessary to draw the attention of teachers to the fact that initially exercises may include arbitrary stretching with the development of fatigue in the lesson, rotation in the shoulder joints without lifting the arms, slow head bends, rubbing the wrists and hands, closing the eyes, rubbing the forehead, slow and deep breathing. Students are well aware of the "blotting out" exercise. These simple exercises help to significantly optimize the functional state of students, without causing, at the same time, feelings of protest. It is particularly relevant to introduce such pauses in 4-6 lessons, when students' performance is noticeably reduced.

In sports sections, the process of organizing the educational and training process and monitoring the health of those involved is significantly different. As D.L. Rudman notes: "The safety requirements for SAMBO classes are as follows:

- 1) Sambo students must undergo introductory and initial safety training at the training site (in the hall);
- 2) students who have not completed safety training are not allowed to attend classes.;
- 3) in the absence of a coach, independent classes of students are prohibited.;
- 4) Before class, jewelry and other foreign objects (chains, rings, watches, etc.) must be removed to avoid injury.;

5) students must follow the rules of internal order in the gym and other rooms.;

6) it is necessary to start and finish performing various exercises and techniques at the signal of the physical education teacher (coach). Only those techniques or exercises that the trainer suggests are performed.;

7) when learning techniques with an increased risk of an unsuccessful fall, students are required to know the necessary insurance and self-insurance techniques. Receptions are performed only within the limits of the carpet (tatami) one meter from its edge. You should fight carefully, avoiding hitting the wall.;

8) before starting classes, it is necessary to remove all foreign objects behind the side and front lines of the carpet. To visit gyms, you must have a change of shoes.

The model of professional competencies of trainers: business and social qualities of a personality, a principled approach to business, will, perseverance, the ability to finish a job, self-demanding, a sense of responsibility, conscientiousness, initiative, the ability to work independently, innovation.

Control and diagnostic skills: they are carried out in the process of analyzing the results of current and final control (individual, input diagnostics, intermediate, output diagnostics), implemented during monitoring. Regulatory and correctional skills: the coach corrects the activities of students using a comparative analysis of the level of achievements, which allows them to track the effectiveness of the educational and training process, and conducts reflection.

Sports selection is the selection of athletes who are most suitable for achieving high results based on their combined individual morphophysiological, as well as mental, personal and other qualities, based on the requirements of a particular sport. Sports selection is carried out with the participation of a sports doctor at all stages of sports training together with a coach. Information and educational promotion of the necessary medical knowledge is aimed at familiarizing instructors of therapeutic gymnastics, physical education teachers, coaches and students with the advantages of rational planning of the rehabilitation and training process, proper use of the effects of hardening factors, acclimatization, chronobiological adaptation, the importance of medical supervision and self-control of athletes."

The coach and the doctor must constantly take special measures to prevent possible diseases and injuries. Let's name the main factors that cause fatigue and the associated means of rehabilitation measures.

Psychological factors: acute mental situations in a competitive environment with the participation of strong opponents; psychological depression caused by injuries, illnesses, family troubles, conflicts with the coach and teammates; stagnation in sports results; unexpected loss to weak and equal opponents; chronic fatigue from previous competitions. To eliminate the violations that have occurred, it is recommended: low-

intensity restorative training with the complete exclusion of competition: the use of outdoor activities with non-specific muscle work; changing the environment in which the athlete trained; the use of autogenic training with functional music, if possible; special means to promote relaxation, for example, a relaxing bath with self-massage.

Educational work should include lectures and talks on the role of special events aimed at eliminating the effects of fatigue as quickly as possible. We need daily monitoring of athletes' compliance with recovery procedures. Finally, athletes should be encouraged to take independent action. The coach must educate his players in such a way that special measures to eliminate fatigue from previous training sessions and competitions as quickly as possible become a habit.

List of used literature:

1. Babushkin G.D. *Общая теория спорта: современные концепции подготовки спортсменов: учебник* / G. D. Babushkin. - Saratov: Vuzovskoe obrazovanie, 2020. - 294 с.
2. Баранцев S.A. *Возрастная биомеханика основных видов движений школьников: монография [Электронный ресурс]: монография - Электрон. дан.* Lan - Moskva: Sovetskiy sport, 2014. - 304 с.
3. Blonskiy P.P. *Развитие мышления школьника [Электронный ресурс]* – Электрон. дан. - Sankt-Peterburg: Lan, 2013. - 93 с.
4. Vinogradov P.A. *Vserossiyskiy fizkulturno-sportivnyy kompleks «Gotov k trudu i oborone» (GTO) – put k zdorovyu i fizicheskomu sovershenstvu [Электронный ресурс]* / P.A. Vinogradov, A.V. Царик, Yu.V. Okunkov. - Электрон. дан. - Moskva, 2016. - 234 с.
5. Garnik V.S. *Sambo: metodika uchebno-trenirovochnykh i samostoyatelnykh zanyatiy. Uchebnoe posobie* / V. S. Garnik. - Moskva: Moskovskiy gosudarstvennyy stroitelnyy universitet, ЭBS ASV, 2012. - 191с.